

Impact of POGIL Instructional Strategy on Academic Confidence and Performance in Genetics Concept among Secondary School Students in Tarauni, Kano State

Gali, Musa¹

galimusa01@gmail.com

08039645468

Muhammad U. Sale¹

mmsaleh2003@gmail.com

08062922002

Sharfadden Shehu¹

sharfaddenshehu@gmail.com

08035669851

Sani A. Muhammd¹

mamu2496@gmail.com

08063092496

Ali H. Chigari¹

aliyu255@gmail.com

08035051755

Zainab Salihi Zakari²

zainabsalihi70@gmail.com

08067138505

¹Department of Integrated Science, Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education, Kumbotso

²Department of Biological Science, Kano State College of Education and Preliminary Studies

Abstract

The study examined the impact of POGIL instructional strategy on academic confidence and performance in genetic concepts among secondary school students in Tarauni, Kano State. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, posttest non randomized control group design. The population of the study consists of 2493 (1,200 Male and 1,293 Female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) government secondary school Biology students in Tarauni, during the 2022/2023 academic session. The Sample size of the study consists of 200 (100 male and 100 female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) government secondary school Biology students. This was arrived at using an intact class from four government secondary schools randomly selected in Tarauni, Kano State. Genetics Concept Performance Test (GCPT) and Student Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) were used to elicit information on performance and academic confidence, respectively. The reliability of the instruments was 0.79 and 0.97. The subjects in the experimental group were taught genetics concepts using POGIL instructional strategy, while the subjects in the control group were taught same concepts using Lecture Method. Two research questions were raised and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviations while null hypotheses were tested using t-test and Mann Whitney at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. The finding of the study showed that there was a significant difference between the performance mean scores of students taught genetics concept using POGIL instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method in favor of experimental group. Therefore, students taught genetic concept using POGIL instructional strategy exhibited high academic confidence and performance when compared with their counterparts taught same concepts using lecture method. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the use of POGIL instructional strategy should be emphasized and use in secondary schools across the state.

Keyword: POGIL instructional strategy, Academic confidence and Performance

Impact of POGIL Instruction... (Gali, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482773>

Introduction

Biology is the scientific study of living organisms and their interaction with each other and their environment. This field encompassed a wide range of topics, including genetics, evolution, ecology, physiology among others. The objectives of teaching Biology as a science subject are based on practical and experiment as contained in the National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013) also included among others are to equip learners with meaningful and relevant knowledge of Biology, adequate laboratory, instructional material and field skills. It is expected that, through utilization of Biology laboratory equipment and other instructional materials that the biology students' academic performance could be and the above objectives and goals can be achieved (Haruna, 2019). Academic performance represents the outcome that indicates the extent to which a student has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in schools. In teaching and learning situations, academic performance is synonymous with academic achievement. They could be seen as the outcome of students' effort in examinations. Okoye, (2018) contended that a student's academic performance is dependent on several factors such as, learning environment, instructional methods and teaching strategy, teachers' attitude and enthusiasm, as well as students' attitude and background. When suitable teaching method is employed during instructional delivery particularly subsumption could improve performance.

Low performance in Biology among Nigerian secondary school students has been the major concern of parents, teachers and the public. This low performance in SSCE Biology examination at credit level may be due to poor methods of teaching and lack of instructional materials among others. Scholars such as Rilwani, Akahomen, and Gbakeji, (2014) have identified several factors influencing students' academic performance in Biology as a course of study including class size, laboratories, instructional strategies, textbooks, guidance and counseling services, academic and professional qualification of teachers, teachers' attributes, students' attributes, peer groups, parental and home background, and school environment among others. Warfa (2016) have shown that the teaching of science (including Biology) in Nigerian secondary schools have fallen short of the standard expected of it as a result of using inappropriate method of instruction. This assertion was supported in the work of science educators like Ali, Toriman and Gasim (2014) who have found that the persistent low academic performance in science education were attributed to teachers' instructional strategies such as lecture method in which the learner remained passive while the teacher is always active. They emphasized that lecture method does not promote meaningful learning of science because differences in students' ability are not considered and it cannot satisfy the individual learning mode. Thus, instructional strategies used by teachers in the teaching and learning process have significant influence on learners' academic performance. This is why Rabi, Toriman and Gasim, (2014) says that for decades, individual and other professional bodies such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) have worked tirelessly to deal decisively with students' poor academic performance in science by developing/innovative teaching strategies that would improve learning of science. Therefore, for effective learning to take place, appropriate method of instruction such as POGIL can be utilized.

Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) is a research-based, student-centered philosophy and science pedagogy in which students work in small groups to engage in guided inquiry using carefully designed materials that direct and guide students to build and rebuild their knowledge (Kim 2016; Roller & Zori 2017). In POGIL activities, students construct their understanding of the content and key process skills such as problem solving, critical thinking skills, application of information, and communication in science, deductive reasoning, self-assessment, teamwork, and time management (Conway, 2014).

A review of the literature shows that there are various studies relating to POGIL instructional strategy. The study by Roller (2015), however, analyzed the effects of POGIL on students' understanding of biological classification. The research found that POGIL was influential in uncovering students' alternative conceptions and in changing them. A review of other studies in the literature concerning POGIL, shows that students' achievement levels have generally risen, and more sustained and in-depth learning has occurred through POGIL (Barthlow, Watson 2014; Vanags, Pammer, & Brinker, 2014. It was also found that students have positive opinions regarding POGIL learning environments (Conway, 2014 and Soltis *et al.*, 2015). BeÂneÂteau et. al. (2016) compared three different teaching methods in science education - problem-based learning (PBL), POGIL and peer-led team learning. The researchers showed that the POGIL method contributed more to the development of students' learning capabilities. Moog (2014), on the other hand, investigated the effects of POGIL method on changing alternative conceptions about the particulate nature of matter. Consequently, it was found that students taught through POGIL had fewer alternative conceptions than those taught using traditional teaching methods.

Various studies have been documented for the effectiveness of POGIL instructional strategy in enhancing students' academic confidence and performance. For example, Kwarteng (2014) and Canelas, Hill and Novicki A. (2017) reported that POGIL improved academic confidence and performance in the course, encouraged active engagement with the material in the class, provided immediate feedback to the instructor concerning student deficits and misunderstandings, and created a positive

Impact of POGIL Instruction... (Gali, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482773>

classroom environment where students enjoyed learning very difficult material. Moog (2014) reported positive gains in students' achievement as their test grades and overall test grades were positively affected by POGIL. Walker and Warfa (2017) have found statistically significant difference in students' academic confidence and performance between two groups, one of which experienced a traditional instructional approach while the other experienced POGIL activities. Therefore, this study examined the impact of POGIL instructional strategy on academic confidence and performance in genetic concepts among secondary school students in Tarauni, Kano State.

Academic confidence according to Honicke & Broadbent (2016) refers to a student's belief in their capabilities to succeed academically. It involves having faith in one's own skills, knowledge, and capacity to learn, which leads to a positive attitude towards academic challenges and tasks. Samikwo (2014) maintained that confidence plays a significant role in students' learning, thus, students with higher level of academic confidence are proved to be high achievers than those with low academic confidence. Allchin (2015) found that the student who perceives himself confident has a high level of academic achievement and student who perceives himself as worthless is less confident and may not come up to the optimum level of attainment. Degale and Boisselle (2015) asserted that academic confidence is believed to affect performance through the influence on task perception. For example, research studies by Sedumedi (2014) and Stevens (2015) suggest that high academic confidence creates a feeling of calmness when approaching a difficult task and conversely, low academic confidence may result in an individual perceiving a task as more difficult than it really is, which leads to stress and a narrowness of ideas when tackling the solution of the problem. Ochoa and Sander (2014) opined that students with low academic confidence enter colleges with lower academic skills and are found to be less engaged and face more transition difficulties than those who enter college with confidence. Sanders, Putwain and Fuente (2015) believe that student academic confidence can change if the student enters into the academic environment where the form and processes of education itself are demystified. This involves giving learning opportunities to refine the students' academic skills. An understanding of students' confidence could be beneficial in helping teachers create more effective learning environments. It helps teachers to understand their students, which enhances the teaching process even if just through a psychometric profile. De Gale and Boisselle (2015) ascertained that academic confidence can develop from the mastery of skills, various experiences and social and emotional support. Students having confidence in academic setting have been found to perform better than students with low confidence in academic setting. Confidence level also affected retention of learned concept. In this study therefore, students' academic confidence was investigated. Therefore, this study examined the impact of POGIL instructional strategy on academic confidence and performance in genetic concepts among secondary school students in Tarauni, Kano State.

Statement of the Research Problem:

In spite of the importance of Biology among Nigerian students, performance at SSCE level remained poor at credit level. This persistent failure in SSCE Biology examination at credit level may be due to poor methods of teaching and lack of instructional materials among others. Some research studies by Albaladejo and Lucas, (2014) shown that students do not fully understand chromosomes, genes, or alleles. Slack and Stewart, (2014) opined that many biology students cannot adequately interpret some concepts such as homozygous or heterozygous. Kindfield, (2016) says that many biology students have alternative views of some processes such as mitosis and meiosis and also they do not understand the meanings of probability in relation to genotype and phenotype frequencies in offspring. Rahamneh, (2017) opined that medium of instruction in teaching biology at post primary/higher education institutions is another factor contributing to poor academic performance in sciences. Low academic confidence has been found to bring about poor performance and it's affected by instructional method which creates stress and apprehension in students. This also affects retention of learned concepts and also affects performance. The use of POGIL instructional strategy has been found to have significant impact on improving student's academic confidence and performance.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. examine the impact of POGIL instruction strategy on academic performance of students taught genetic concept.
2. determine the impact of POGIL instruction strategy on academic confidence of students taught genetic concept.

Research Questions

This study provided the following research questions:

1. What is the difference between mean academic performance scores of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method?
2. What is the difference between mean academic confidence scores of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method?

Null Hypotheses

Impact of POGIL Instruction... (Gali, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482773>

The following Null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between mean academic confidence of students taught Genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, posttest non randomized control group design. The population of the study consists of 2493 (1,200 Male and 1,293 Female) senior secondary school class two (SSII) government secondary school Biology students in Tarauni, during the 2022/2023 academic session. Simple random sampling, involving balloting method was used to select four schools out of the twenty-one (21) in the population. This was done by written the name of all the schools that make up the population on a piece of paper and a child was asked to pick four (4) papers randomly. Four schools selected were assigned into control and experimental groups respectively. From the four (4) schools, one intact class of SSII was selected using balloting method of simple random sampling because they were found to be equivalent. This gave a total number of four (4) intact classes for the study, which were randomly assigned into control and experiment groups. Thus, the total sample for the study stood at 200.

Instrumentations

Two instruments, Genetics Concept Performance Test (GCPT) and Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) were used for the study. GCPT was adapted from past questions papers of WAEC and NECO and Biology textbooks, which consisted of thirty-five (35) items with multiple choice of letters A-D. GCPT was used for pretest and posttest in order to measure the level of performance among SSII Biology students while the Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) was adapted from Sander and Sanders, (2005) and used to measure student's academic confidence. The SACI has 12 items of Likert 5-scale involving Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U) Disagree (DA) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Each of the options carried weight in order of priority from 5 – 1 in positive confidence responses and from 1- 5 in negative confidence responses. Students were asked to freely indicate their confidence in genetic concept of biology by ticking one of the responses that suits their interest.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The instruments Genetic Concept Performance Test (GCPT) and Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) were validated by three experts. The instruments were revised and corrected in the light of responses of expert opinions, pilot testing, difficulty level and discriminating Index. The final version of tests consisted of thirty-five (35) questions. Then item difficulty level and Discrimination index was calculated for each item as a response of 100 students from different schools in the study area. The reliability of a research instrument concerns the extent to which the instrument yields the same results on repeated trials. To determine the reliability coefficient of Genetic Concept Performance Test (GCPT) and Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) a test-retest method was employed to a trial-testing group who were found to be equivalent in all aspects to the students in the study. After a two weeks interval the second test was administered to the same group of students in line with Tuckman's (1975) recommendation on the use of two-week interval for test-retest method. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used for the analysis. From the result obtained, the reliability of the instruments was found to be 0.75 and 0.79 for both instruments. This signifies that there is strong positive relationship between the first and second administration of GCPT and SACI.

Procedure for data collection and analysis

For effective data collection, the four groups (one experimental and one control group) were taught separately for the period of six weeks. Genetic Concept Performance Test (GCPT) was administered to both groups at the beginning which serve as a pretest. The essence of pretest is to ensure that the selected schools were not significantly different in terms of abilities before actual treatment. The selected sampled schools were taught genetic concept for the period of six weeks. The posttest was administered to the four groups in order to determine the effect of the treatment. After two-week, Post posttest was administered to all groups in order to determine their retention level of the genetic concept. Student's Academic Confidence Inventory (SACI) was administered to both experimental and control groups, before and after the treatment in order to determine their academic confidence level. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The null hypotheses were analyzed and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance using t-test and Mann Whitney.

Impact of POGIL Instruction... (Gali, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482773>

Results

Research Question1: What is the difference between mean academic performance scores of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method? The detail of the results is presented in Table 1.1

Table 1.1 Descriptive Statistics on difference between the performance mean scores of students taught Genetics Concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using the Lecture Method.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std.Err	M D
Academic performance	Exp.	100	29.49	5.265	.526	16.77
	Control	100	12.72	3.452	.345	

Table 1.1 showed that difference existed between the performance mean scores of students taught Genetics Concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using the Lecture method. The computed performance mean scores for the experimental and control groups are 29.49 and 12.72 respectively, and their mean difference was 16.71. This implies that students in the experimental group had higher mean scores compared to those in the control group.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

Table 1.2: Independent t-test statistics on difference between performance mean scores of students taught Genetics concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using the Lecture method.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	S.Dev	Std.Err	M D	Df	t-cal	P
Academic performance	Exp.	100	29.49	5.27	.526	16.77	198	26.63	0.00
	Control	100	12.72	3.45	345				

Calculated $p < 0.05$ computed $t > 1.96$ at df 198

Table 1.2 showed that significant differences existed between the performance mean scores of students taught Genetics concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using the Lecture method. Reasons being that the calculated p level of 0.00 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and the computed t value of 26.63 is higher than the 1.96 t-critical values at df 198. Their computed performance mean scores are 29.49 and 12.72 of students taught Genetics Concept using Ausubel's Subsumption Instructional Strategy and those taught using the Lecture method in favour of the experimental groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis one rejected.

Research Question 2: What is the difference between mean academic confidence scores of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method? The detail of the results is presented in Table 1.3

Table 1.3 Mean Ranking statistic of Academic confidence of the Experimental Group (EG) and Control Group (CG)

Academic confidence		N	Mean Rank	Sum of rank	Mean gain
Experimental group	(Pretest)	100	43.62	6151.00	
	(Posttest)		54.43	6243.00	10.81
Control group	(Pretest)	100	40.88	5151.00	
	(Posttest)		33.42	4051.00	7.46
Total		200			

Table 1.3 shows the academic confidence mean rank of experimental group exposed to POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method. The experimental group has mean rank of 43.62 before the treatment and 54.43 after the treatment with mean gain of 10.81, while the control group (CG) has mean rank of 40.88 before the treatment and 33.42 with mean loss of 7.46. This indicates that the academic confidence of the experimental groups taught genetics concept using POGIL

Impact of POGIL Instruction... (Gali, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482773>

instruction strategy has improved after the treatment while those in the control group exposed to lecture method showed reduction in their academic confidence after the treatment.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between mean academic confidence of students taught Genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those exposed to lecture method. The detail of the results is presented in Table 1.4

Table 1.4 Non Parametric test of Mann Whitney on academic confidence of Experimental Groups (EG) and Control Group (CG)

Variable	Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney	Z	P
Academic confidence	Experimental group	100	45.44	14543.50	300.50	11.400	0.002
	Control group	100	40.03	5157.50			
	Total	200					

Table 1.4 shows the results of Non Parametric test of Mann Whitney on academic confidence of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using lecture method. The mean rank of experimental group academic confidence is 45.44 while the control group has the mean rank of 40.03 respectively. The calculated p value of 0.002 of the experimental groups is lower than 0.05 alpha level of significance. This shows clearly that students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy have higher academic confidence than students taught the same concept using lecture method. Therefore, null hypothesis 2 is hereby rejected. The result of finding is in favour of the experimental group because they have higher academic confidence.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1.3 shows that there was a significant different between performance mean score of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instructional strategy and those taught the same concept using lecture method. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Soltis, Verlinden, Kruger, Carroll and Trumbo (2015) who reported positive gains in students' performance using this method. Also Vishnumolakala, Southam, Treagust, Mocerino and Qureshi (2017) reported that students' test grades and overall test grades were positively affected by POGIL and they also stressed that POGIL improved performance in the course, encouraged active engagement with the material in the class, provided immediate feedback to the instructor concerning student deficits and misunderstandings, and created a positive classroom environment where students enjoyed learning very difficult material. The finding of this study contradict the finding of Warfa, (2016) who showed no significant differences between the performance of students who were in a POGIL-based section of a course compared with those who were in a traditionally taught section.

The result of Table 1.4 revealed that there was a significant difference between the academic confidence of students taught genetic concept using POGIL instruction strategy and those taught using lecture method in favour of the experimental group. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Salih and Ahmed (2015) who investigated the impact of academic confidence on EFL Sudanese tertiary level students Department of English language at El-Imam El-Mahdi University and White Nile College for Science and Technology in the White Nile State. The findings of their study revealed a positive, significant correlation between academic confidence, and academic performance. The finding of this study contradict the finding of Degale and Boisselle (2015) who found no statistically significant difference in students' confidence between two groups, one of which experienced a traditional instructional approach while the other used POGIL activities. Also, Sadiq and Mehwish (2014) studied "University Students' academic confidence between Social Sciences and Natural Science students Pakistan. Their finding indicated that control group held significantly higher levels of academic confidence than experimental group.

Conclusion

It has been concluded that POGIL instructional strategy can improve academic performance of students taught genetics concept if properly implemented. This is evident in the finding of hypothesis one that students taught genetics concepts in the experimental group has significantly higher performance mean scores than their counterparts taught same concept using the Lecture Method. Also, POGIL instructional strategy can improve academic confidence of students in the experimental groups if properly implemented. This is evident in the finding of hypothesis two that students in the experimental group taught genetics concepts using the POGIL instruction strategy have significantly higher academic confidence mean rank scores when compared with students in the control group. This infers that POGIL instruction strategy can improve academic confidence.

Impact of POGIL Instruction... (Gali, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482773>

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the followings recommendations a made:

1. The use of POGIL instruction strategy should be emphasized and rigorously implemented in secondary schools across the state because students taught using tis instructional strategy exhibited remarkable academic confidence and performance when compared with their counterparts taught using the lecture method
2. Curriculum planners should examine the effectiveness of POGIL instruction strategy and consider it suitability for teaching science concepts since it has the potential of bringing about meaningful learning and improving academic confidence and performance.
3. Organizations such as the STAN, the NERDC should organize seminars, workshop and conferences on the use of POGIL instruction strategy for science teachers at the secondary school level for better implementation and utilization of the method.
4. The use of POGIL instruction strategy should be incorporated into the Biology teacher training curricula at NCE and BSc. Ed Bio program in order to produce teachers who are able to use POGIL instruction strategy in the teaching and learning process.

References

- Ali, A.R., Toriman, M.E. & Gasim, M.B. (2014). Academic Achievement in Biology with Suggested Solutions in Selected Secondary Schools in Kano State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research Vol. 2 No. (11) 10-15*
- Allchin, D. (2015). Problem- and Case-Based Learning in Science: An Introduction to Distinctions, Values, and Outcomes. *CBE-Life Sciences Education 12*, 364-372
- Barthlow, M.J. & Watson S.B. (2014) The effectiveness of process-oriented guided-inquiry learning to reduce alternative conceptions in secondary chemistry. *School Sci. Math.*, 114 (5), 246-255
- BeÂneÂteau C, Fox G, Holcomb J, Xu X, Lewis J, Ramachandran K, & Campbell S. (2016) Peer led guided inquiry in calculus at the university of South Florida. *J STEM Educ.*, 17 (2), 5-13
- Campbell, N. (2014). Process oriented guided inquiry learning to enhance learning of concepts in a biochemistry lab. *The FASEB Journal*, 28(1), 618-629
- Canelas D.A, Hill J.L, & Novicki A. (2017) Cooperative learning in organic chemistry increases student assessment of learning gains in key transferable skills. *Chem. Educ. Res. Pract.*, Advance Article, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7RP00014F>
- Chase, A., Pakhira, D., & Stains, M. (2014). Implementing Process-Oriented, Guided-Inquiry Learning for the First Time: Adaptations and Short-Term Impacts on Students' Attitude and Performance. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 90(4), 409-416.
- Conway, C. J. (2014). Effects of guided inquiry versus lecture instruction on final grade distribution in a one-semester organic and biochemistry course. *Journal of Chemical Education*, (9)1, 480-483
- De Gale, S. & Boisselle, L. N. (2015). The effect of POGIL on academic performance and academic confidence. *Science Education International*, 26 (1), 56-79.
- Degale, S. & Boisselle, L.N. (2015). The effect of POGIL on academic performance and academic confidence. *Science Education International* 26, (1) 56-79
- FME, (2013) *National Policy on Education*. Yaba, National Educational Resource Development Centre Press.
- Freeman S, Eddy SL, McDonough M, Smith MK, Okoroafor N, & Jordt H,. (2014) Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proc Natl Acad Sci.*, 111 (23), 8410-8415
- Hanson, R & Apple, J. N (2014).An exploration of experiences in using the hybrid MOODLE Approach in the delivery and learning situations at the University of Education, Winneba, Ghana. *Journal of Education and Practice*. Vol. (5), 12 102-113
- Haruna, A.S. (2019). Preference for Teacher's Gender among undergraduate students of Science Education in Federal College of Education, Kano. *Kano Journal of Educational Psychology* 1 (1), 102 – 111.
- Honicke, T., & Broadbent, J. (2016) The influence of academic self-efficacy on academic performance: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 17, 63-84.
- Kim, J.J. (2016) *Process-oriented guided-inquiry learning (POGIL) in high school chemistry setting*. Master's Thesis, California State University, Northridge, CA.

Impact of POGIL Instruction... (Gali, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482773>

- Kindfield, A. C. H. (2016) Understanding a basic biological process: Expert and novice models of meiosis. *Science Education, Vol.(7) 8*, 255-283.
- Kuhn D, Arvidsson TS, Lespérance K, & Corprew R. (2017) Can engaging in science practices promote deep understanding of them? *Science Education*, 101 (2), 232-250
- Kwarteng, M. (2014) The effectiveness Process Oriented Guided Inquiry learning to reduce alternative conceptions in Secondary Chemistry. *School Science and Mathematics*, 114 (5) 246 – 255.
- Moog R. (2014) *Process oriented guided inquiry learning*. In McDaniel M. A., Frey R. F., Fitzpatrick S. M., & Roediger H. L. (Eds.), Integrating cognitive science with innovative teaching in STEM disciplines. St. Louis: Washington University in St. Louis Libraries. [Ereader version] <http://dx.doi.org/10.7936/K7PN93HC>, pp147-166,
- Ochoa, A. R. A, & Sander, P. (2014). Contrasting academic behavioural confidence in Mexican and European psychology students, *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 10(2), 252-260
- Okoye, K. (2018) Effects of Lecture Demonstration and Lecture Teaching Methods on Students' Achievement in Biology with suggested solutions in selected secondary schools in Kano State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, Vol. 2 (1) 102-114
- Rabiu A. A, Toriman M. E & Gasim M. Z. (2014). Academic Achievement in Biology with suggested solutions in selected secondary schools in Kano State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, Vol. (2), 11 231-237
- Rahamneh, K. F. A., (2017). Reasons for the Low Academic Achievements among the Students of the Main Stages in Selected Schools in the Province of Al-Balqa. *Ozean Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol (5), 1, 31-40
- Rilwani, M. L, Akahomen, D. & Gbakeji, J. (2014) Secondary school students' attrition in Geography in Esan West Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria: The teachers' perspective. *International Journal of Education and Research*, Vol. (2) 11 112-203
- Roller, M.C. & Zori S. (2017) The impact of instituting process-oriented guided-inquiry learning (POGIL) in a fundamental nursing course. *Nurse Education Today*, 50, 72-76,
- Roller, M.C. (2015) Fundamental nursing: Process-oriented inquiry-learning (POGIL) research. *Journal of Leadership and Instruction*, 1(2) 20-23
- Sadiq, M., & Mehwish, L. (2014) University Students' Academic Confidence: Comparison between Social Sciences and Natural Science Disciplines. *Journal of Elementary Education* Vol. (2) 2 113-123
- Salih, A. A. A. & Ahmed, G. A. A. (2015) The Impact of academic confidence on Efl Sudanese Tertiary Level Students Department of English language at El-Imam El-Mahdi University and White Nile College for Science and Technology in the White Nile State. *International Journal of Information Research and Review*. 2 (9), 1093-1106,
- Samikwo, C., (2014). Factors which influence academic performance in Biology in Kenya. A case of selected secondary schools in Uasin-Gishu West District. <http://hdl.handle.net/123456789/1696>
- Sanders, P., Putwain, D. & Fuente, L. J. (2014). Relationship between undergraduate student confidence approach to learning and academic performance: the role of gender, *Revistade Psicodidactica*, 8 Vol. (2). 231-240
- Sedumedi, T. (2014). The use Productive Inquiry in the teaching of problem solving in chemical stoichiometry. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 15 (20) 1346- 1359
- Slack, S. J. & Stewart, J. H. (2014) High school students' problem-solving performance on realistic genetics problems. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 27, 55-67.
- Soltis, R., Verlinden, N., Kruger, N., Carroll, A., & Trumbo, T. (2015). Process-oriented guided inquiry learning strategy enhances students' higher level thinking skills in a pharmaceutical sciences course. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 79 (1), 1-8.
- Soltis, R., Verlinden, N., Kruger, N., Carroll, A., & Trumbo, T. (2015). Process-oriented guided inquiry learning strategy enhances students' higher level thinking skills in a pharmaceutical sciences course. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 79(1), 1-8.
- Stevens, T. G. (2015). Self -confidence. Retrieved from <http://www.csulb.edu>.
- Villagonzalo, E.C. (2014). Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning: An effective Approach in Enhancing Students' Academic Performance. Presented at the DLSU Research congress 2014, De La Salle University, Manila, Philippines, March 6-8, 2014

Impact of POGIL Instruction... (Gali, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482773>

- Vishnumolakala, V. R., Southam, D. C., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., & Qureshi, S. (2017). Students' attitudes, self-efficacy and experiences in a modified process-oriented guided inquiry learning undergraduate chemistry classroom. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 18(2), 340-352. doi:10.1039/c6rp00233a
- Walker L, & Warfa A-RM (2017) Process oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) marginally effects student achievement measures but substantially increases the odds of passing a course. PLoS ONE 12(10): 186-203. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186203>
- Warfa A. (2016) Using Cooperative Learning to Teach Chemistry: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Journal of Chem Educ.*, 93 (2), 248-255,
- Warfa, A.R. M. (2016). Using Cooperative Learning To Teach Chemistry: A Meta-analytic Review. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 93(2), 248-255.
- Whittington C.P., Pellock, S.J, Cunningham, R.L. & Cox J.R. (2014) Combining content and elements of communication into an upper-level biochemistry course, *Biochem. Mol. Biol. Educ.*, 42 (2), 165-173
- Wozniak, B. M. (2014). *Effect of process-oriented guided-inquiry learning on non-majors' biology students' understanding of biological classification* (Order No. 1517251). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1039584600). Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/docview/1039584600?accountid=11248>